

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH OF IRON-CONTAINING SORBENTS ON THE BASIS OF ORGANOMONTMORYLLONITE FOR THE EXTRACTION OF Cr(VI)

Zhdaniuk N.

*Ph.D., National Technical University of Ukraine
"Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute",
Victory Ave, 37, Kyiv, Ukraine, 03056*

Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of the structure and sorption properties of composites based on clay minerals. The materials are designed to clean aquatic environments from contamination by heavy metals and radionuclides. Physicochemical and technological features of obtaining sorbents on the basis of organomodified montmorillonite with a layer of nanosized zero-valent iron are considered. Their structure was studied using X-ray diffraction, microscopic studies, as well as their sorption capacity with respect to Cr (VI).

Keywords: nanosized zero-valent iron, montmorillonite, organo montmorillonite, sorption, chromium (VI).

Introduction. Sorption methods are the most promising for the extraction of heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions, especially their low concentrations. Recently, research aimed at the synthesis of highly selective sorption materials based on clay minerals has developed significantly. In order to increase the sorption capacity of clay minerals, it is promising to modify their surface with nanosized zero-valent iron (Fe^0). This material is widely used for purification of aqueous solutions from inorganic pollutants due to its physicochemical properties. Fe^0 nanoparticles have a large surface area, which provides high sorption properties. However, one of the most important properties of nanosized iron is its ability to exhibit reducing properties. Thus, by converting pollutants into less harmful ones, for example, the reduction of Cr (VI) to Cr (III).

A significant disadvantage is that Fe^0 tends to aggregate and is easily oxidized. These factors reduce the activity and efficiency of nanosized zero-valent iron. However, Fe^0 synthesized on the surface of clay minerals remains virtually unchanged in the environment.

Research methods: Montmorillonite is a layered silicate with the general formula $(\text{Ca}, \text{Na})(\text{Al}, \text{Mg}, \text{Fe})_2(\text{OH})_2 [(\text{Si}, \text{Al})_4\text{O}_{10}] \times n\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Purification of montmorillonite was performed according to the method described in the article [1]. In this work, pre-prepared clay, converted into Na-form, was treated with cationic surfactants - salts of four-substituted ammonium with different alkyl chain lengths from the manufacturer Merck: hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (HDTMA) [2]. In this work, the synthesis of nanosized zero-valent iron (Fe^0) was performed by the sulfate method without the use of an inert atmosphere according to the methods [3,4]. Then the obtained nanomaterial (Fe^0 , Fe^0 -MMT, Fe^0 -OMMT) was separated from the liquid phase by centrifugation and washed three times with alcohol. The obtained materials were dried under vacuum at a temperature of 90°C and ground to obtain a fraction ≤ 0.1 mm. Chemically pure reagents $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, NaBH_4 and HDTMA manufactured by Merck were used in the experiments.

The structure of sorbents was investigated by X-ray diffraction and microscopic studies, as well as the sorption capacity of Cr (VI) ions.

X-ray diffraction studies of the original and modified samples were performed using a DRON-4-07 diffractometer with two Soller slits using filtered $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation in the range of $3-60^\circ$ (2θ). Electron microscopic studies. TEM studies were performed on a PEM-U transmission electron microscope with a digital image output system SAI-01A using Lacey formv / carb 400M CU PK25 grids manufactured by Ted pella, Inc. SEM study was performed on a scanning electron microscope REM-106I.

Sorption extraction of Cr (VI) with clay minerals, nano-iron and composite silicate materials was performed under static conditions at room temperature, determined ionic strength and continuous shaking of samples for 1 hour (volume of aqueous phase was 50 cm^3 , sorbent weight - 0.1 g for determination of Cr(VI) sorption. After adsorption equilibrium was established, the aqueous phase was separated by centrifugation and the equilibrium concentration of the metal ion was determined spectrophotometrically on a UNICO 2100UV instrument using the nitroso-R-salt reagent diphenylcarbazide ($\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}$).

Results. On the diffraction pattern of nanosized iron we observe clear reflexes at 44.9° and 35.8° (0.202 and 0.252 nm, respectively) belonging to the crystalline phases of zero-valent iron (α -Fe) and iron oxide (FeO). The diffractograms of MMT and OMMT samples after application of a layer of nanosized iron also recorded reflexes at 44.9° and 35.8° , indicating the presence in the composition of composite sorbents of crystalline phases of zero-ferrous iron, iron oxide, as well as, at lower values of 2θ , goethite (FeOOH) [2].

Studies (SEM) were also performed for Fe^0 and Fe^0 -OMMT samples. The Fe^0 sample is characterized by the formation of branch-like structures (Pic. 1.1). Iron particles form nanospheres that connect to each other in chains. This linear orientation is related to the magnetic properties of iron. For the Fe^0 -MMT sample (Pic. 1.2) there is a uniform distribution of Fe^0 particles on the surface of mineral, as well as the characteristic distribution of nanosized iron as individual aggregates and chain clusters.

Pic. 1 – SEM image of the surface of the sample Fe^0 and Fe^0 -OMMT

Comparison of the results of TEM studies of synthesized nanosized Fe^0 and iron-containing composites Fe^0 -OMMT indicates a significant difference in the dispersed structure. The particle size of iron obtained from $FeSO_4$ salt solutions is in the range from tens to several hundred nanometers, which are combined into a continuous spatial grid (Pic. 2.1). The study (TEM) of the

Fe^0 -OMMT sample confirms that nanodispersed iron deposited in OMMT dispersions has a size of 20-80 nm, which is much less than when precipitating iron from $FeSO_4$ solution.

Pic. 2 – TEM image of the surface of the sample Fe^0 and Fe^0 -OMMT

Investigation of sorption removal of Cr (VI) by modified clays based on montmorillonite. The efficiency of extraction of chromium (VI) ions of iron-containing composite based on organomontmorillonite (Fe^0 -OMMT) was compared with the sorption capacity of MMT, OMMT, synthesized nanosized Fe^0 , and Fe^0 -MMT. Sorption experiments were performed on five samples at pH = 6. The obtained isotherms are shown in Pic. 3. The maximum value of Cr (VI) sorption was obtained for the Fe^0 -OMMT composite (22,5 mg/g), which is significantly higher than for Fe^0 -MMT (18,7

mg/g) and nanosized iron Fe^0 (13,2 mg/g). Sorption on the original montmorillonite of anionic forms of Cr(VI) is 2,3 mg/g, and on its organomodified form – 10,8 mg/g.

The increase in the activity of Fe^0 -OMMT composite samples compared to other iron-containing samples is explained by the greater dispersion of nano-iron particles formed on the hydrophobic surface of organomontmorillonite compared to those on the hydrophilic surface of the original montmorillonite particles or simply in solution [5].

Pic. – 3. Isotherms of sorption of Cr (VI) source montmorillonite and synthesized sorbents at pH = 6 (1 - MMT, 2 - OMMT, 3 - Fe⁰, 4 - Fe⁰-MMT, 5 - Fe⁰-OMMT)

Thus, it is confirmed that organomontmorillonite modified with nanosized iron effectively removes chromium(VI) from the aqueous medium at pH close to natural waters, which indicates the possibility of its use in their purification from heavy metal anions and radionuclides.

Conclusions. Composite sorbents based on organomodified montmorillonite with a layer of nanosized Fe⁰ were obtained. It was found that the treatment of organomontmorillonite with nanodispersed iron improves the sorption properties of natural silicates in relation to Cr(VI) compounds, 22,5 mg/g for chromium(VI), which significantly exceeds the value for the original montmorillonite and montmorillonite with Fe⁰ layer.

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